

Quantum Velocity Direction, Information and Negative Wavefunction Values

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In classical mechanics a constant velocity may be defined by dx/dt where x is in the direction of motion. Thus two dimensions are required and the concept of positive/negative x . Quantum mechanics of a free particle involves a $v=x/t$, but also independent periodic fluctuations of x and t i.e. $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ may be considered separately. One, however, cannot lose information we argue so two dimensions are still required to describe motion only using x as well as a concept of negative and positive. (The notion of “only using x ” applies to a bound problem.) If the two dimensions only depend on x , then there is no a priori dimension which may be strictly positive such as t . Both dimensions should allow for positive and negative values so that somehow overall the direction of velocity may be defined.

Quantum mechanics is concerned with probabilities, but classical probabilities do not introduce negative values. As argued in previous notes, it is possible to have two layers of probabilities $P(x)$ (classical) and $P(p/x)$ linked to $\exp(ipx)$ (quantum). The second result contains the two required dimensions and the negative/positive quality.

As argued in (1) a quantum free particle has a velocity $v=x/t$, but the classical action $= -Et+px$ is unchanged if $t=1/E$ and $x=1/p$. Thus we argue that there may be periodic fluctuations about the classical motion $v=x/t$. In other words there are uncoupled t and x fluctuations which are linked to p (i.e. v) and are systematic and periodic. These define spatial density. $v=x/t$ defines velocity and has two dimensions and the notion of positive and negative x . We argue that the fluctuation scheme must also define velocity and so requires two dimensions and a notion of positive/negative. As a result the mathematical result of a wavefunction component $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$ taking on a negative value accounts for information which cannot be lost. For a particle with a single p in a box with infinite walls, a positive or negative hump represents the same probability ($\sin(px)\sin(px) C$), but one does not account for the direction of motion. Even using one dimension $\cos(px)$ as in a bound state problem, the information of negative and positive values must be retained (in $\cos(px)$ over x) because the negative/positive property is used to define overall velocity (even if it is 0 on average for a particle in a box). Thus the concept of interference arises because one cannot lose information in the quantum probabilistic scheme. As noted before it seems one defines new “density” and kinetic energy dimension $\exp(ipx)$ and $pp/2m \exp(ipx)$ etc.

Classical Action and Quantum Free Particle

A classical free particle moves according to $v=dx/dt = x/t$ if x is measured from the origin. X may be positive or negative and two dimensions are required namely x and t to define velocity in one direction. The classical action is relativistically $A = -m_0 t \sqrt{1-vv}$ and nonrelativistically $.5m_0 t vv$ with $c=1$. Both may be rewritten as $A = -Et+px$ (using $v=x/t$) which is a Lorentz invariant. An interesting feature noted in (1) is that though x and t depend on each other through $v=x/t$ there can be independent fluctuations such that when $t_1=1/E$ and $x_1=1/p$, A is unchanged. As a result we argued that a particle may move along with $v=x/t$, but have independent systematic periodic fluctuations in x and t with the cycle in t having a period of $1/E$ and the

wavelength in x being proportional to $1/p$. Thus steady $v=x/t$ motion is needed first to define $E=pp/2m$ and $p=mv$, but then cyclic fluctuations may occur about these values which affect the spatial density ($\exp(ipx)$). In other words v and p are the same everywhere, but fluctuations cause the density to change such that A is the same at the periodic t and x points.

Information

We argue that this periodic motion which depends on v must also carry the same information that velocity carries, namely two dimensions and a positive/negative value. Given that x and t fluctuate independently one no longer has two dimensions supplied by these two variables. For example, one might describe a bound state by only x as is done in quantum mechanics, yet the overall idea of velocity in one direction must still hold. Thus one needs two dimensions and a positive/negative sense. The positive/negative sense should apply to both dimensions it seems, because both depend on x . One does not have a special dimension t which is strictly positive.

Given that $v=x/t$ implies $P(x)=\text{constant}$, one needs a fluctuation scheme which is two dimensional and leads to this same result. It must also have a positive/negative sense to describe the direction of velocity. A basic equation of periodicity i.e. a ray of unit length fixed at one end and moving in a circle is:

$$\cos(kx)\cos(kx) + \sin(kx)\sin(kx) = 1 \quad \text{or} \quad \exp(-ipx) \exp(ipx) = 1 \quad ((1))$$

$\exp(ipx)$ represents two dimensions, maps into $P(x) = \text{constant}$ and provides a positive/negative sense in both dimensions i.e. $\cos(kx)$ and $\sin(kx)$. If $k \rightarrow -k$, $\cos(kx) \rightarrow \cos(kx)$, but $\sin(kx) \rightarrow -\sin(kx)$ allowing for an overall sense of velocity to be defined. What is interesting is that for this to occur, both positive and negative values of $\cos(kx)$ and $\sin(kx)$ occur in each dimension. Thus even if one uses $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ as probabilities and considers a particle moving back and forth in an infinite well and argues that $\sin(kx)$ and $-\sin(kx)$ eliminate each other if $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ add as probabilities, $2\cos(px)$ still contains positive and negative values. For a particle in a well with infinite walls, the spatial density is the same whether $\cos(px) = a$ or $\cos(px) = -a$, but nevertheless the positive negative cycling values must be maintained to maintain an overall sense of velocity direction. As a result there is interference if one adds various $\exp(ipx)$'s as in:

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

which is a solution of the time-independent Schrodinger equation. Even in a bound state in which one dimension disappears due to interference (e.g. particle in a well with infinite walls) and one does not consider direction of motion, the negative/positive information remains. As noted this is the source of interference which leads to various spatial density profiles.

Different Geometry of Space?

It may be noted that both $P(x)=\text{constant}$ linked to $v=x/t$ and $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$ and the sinusoidal density $\cos(kx)\cos(kx)$ have physical meaning. The first, which is classical, seems to be a kind of coarse grained density in the sense that $\exp(ipx)$ is able to pick up details (e.g. phase shifts) etc which do not appear in $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$, but may be revealed through more sensitive interference measurement involving interactions at the scale of a wavelength so $\cos(kx)\cos(kx)$ is real.

It was noted above that $v=x/t$ involves two dimensions and a sense of positive/negative. It is only x , however, one of the dimensions which may take on positive or negative values and the two dimensions are always present even if one considers the average motion of a particle in a box. In such a case average velocity is zero, but average kinetic energy is not.

$v=x/t$ is a driver for the quantum case for a fixed m_0 (rest mass) because $p=m_0 v$ in the nonrelativistic situation. Given this value, however, it is independent fluctuations in x and t which describe the system, its density due to periodic fluctuations and how it interacts. A description in x alone must lead to two dimensions, so one cannot have one represent positive/negative values and the other not i.e. $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ may both be positive or negative. This represents a different geometry of space with periodic concentrations of density and absences of density. $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ represent shifted distributions i.e. distributions at different times. For a particle in a box with infinite walls, $p=mv$ is always present, but one dimension drops out, but the unusual geometry of high and low density does not. If there is only one p present, then this geometry is "in synch" with p and $-p$ motion i.e. $\cos(px)$ and $\cos(-px)$ are the same. If one averages over different p 's then they are not "in synch" and positive and negative high values of $\cos(px)$ establish the density, but also the kinetic energy density. Thus a high negative value (or a high positive value of $\cos(px)$ multiplied by positive kinetic energy) may cancel with a somewhat lower positive value of $\cos(p_1x)$ (or $\cos(p_1x)$ multiplied by kinetic energy). Thus the two dimensions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ define a new kind of geometry which nevertheless when coarse grained so to speak yields back $P(x)=1$ because $\cos(px)$ is based on $p=m_0 v$ and $v=x/t$ is associated with $P(x)=\text{constant}$ classically.

For a distribution $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \exp(ipx)$ averaging over various kinetic energy dimensions (one for each p) i.e. $\{\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx)\} / W(x)$ yields the coarse grained classical kinetic energy $KE(x) = E_n - V(x)$, albeit at special energy values E_n which are discrete.

Physical Nature of the Positive/Negative Values?

As argued a positive/negative sense is required when describing motion only using x . This positive/negative sense does not physically appear for a particle in a box with infinite walls because $\cos(kx_1)=a$ and $\cos(kx_2) = -a$ have the same $P(x)$ density aa . In other words a negative hump and positive hump represent the same density and cannot be distinguished at the $P(x)$ level. At the wavefunction level, however, the positive/negative sense is used partly to define the overall sense of velocity direction. This sense together with two dimensions allows one to have motion to the right or left, but given that the system is moving with $v=x/t$ as well it is

possible that the positive/negative values are linked to fluctuations to the right or left of the overall motion. This may explain why one dimension cancels when adding $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$. Thus there should be some kind of physical scenario linked to the positive/negative values of $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$, but the exact nature of it may not be explicitly described by $\exp(ipx)$. One may note that $\sum a(p) \exp(ipx)$ is a superposition of conditional probabilities which yields an overall $W(x)$ from which one finds $W^*(x)W(x)=P(x)$ which is the classical density.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that $v=x/t$ for a free particle still holds in quantum mechanics and is used to define nonrelativistic momentum $p=m_0 v$ (or relativistic $p=mv/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$). The classical action, both relativistically and nonrelativistically is $A = -Et+px$ so A is unchanged at periodic values of $t=1/E$ and $x=1/p$. Thus we suggest there may be an overall $v=x/t$ constant motion with periodic independent fluctuations in x and t . As a result, one may consider t and x as independent for a free particle in this fluctuation picture. A time fluctuation occurs every $t_1=b/E$ and a spatial one every $x_1=b/p$.

Nevertheless the information required for velocity i.e. two dimensions and a positive/negative sense to define forward and backwards motion remains. The unusual result is that instead of having two dimensions which always remain (i.e. x and t) and only one, namely x , associated with positive and negative values, one may describe spatial density and kinetic energy space for a free particle in terms of two periodic dimensions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. Both of these may have negative and positive values, but these only manifest if different p values interfere. For p and $-p$, one dimension ($\sin(px)$) drops out, but $\cos(px)$ and $\cos(-px)$ are in synch. Even if one multiplies each $\exp(ipx)$ by the positive value $p/2m$ in $\{\sum a(p) p/2m \exp(ipx)\} / \{\sum a(p) \exp(ipx)\}$ positive and negative values of different $\cos(px)$ terms can “interfere” as if different kinetic energy dimensions were interfering to create a coarse grained classical result. The $\cos(px)$ values represent reality in the sense that they are manifested in interference experiments (two slit etc), but $\exp(ipx)$ also maps into $P(x) = 1$ (constant) because it is based on $v=x/t$ which classically is associated with $P(x)=\text{constant}$. It is only if there are interactions on the level of a wavelength proportional to $1/p$ (i.e. the systematic fluctuation) that one gains information related to this length scale.

References

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2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Dynamical Probability Wave (preprint, zenodo, 2022)